

THE ROLE OF A CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY CAMPAIGN ON THE CHARITABLE BEHAVIOR OF THE SOCIETY: CASE STUDY OF COCA-COLA COMPANY AND EDHI FOUNDATION IN PAKISTANI CONTEXT

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Abstract:

Our research work is focused on the “Bottle of Change” campaign, which was launched by Coca-Cola Company Pakistan in 2017 with the collaboration of the Edhi Foundation. The main objective of this campaign was to collect donations for the Edhi Foundation every month of Ramazan. All over Pakistan’s people gave the positive response of the “Bottle of Change” campaign. Thus, this campaign has also been repeated in 2018 and 2019.

1. Introduction

On the beginning of the third millennium, successful businesses, all around the world, have been focusing on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). CSR does not only describe the economic profit, but it also contains social welfare returns (Freeman & Hasnaoui, 2011; McWilliams & Siegel, 2001). Thus, CSR can be defined as “a commitment to improve community well-being through discretionary business practices and contributions of corporate resources” (Kotler & Lee, 2005).

Under the umbrella of CSR, Kotler and Lee (2005) discussed the different CSR initiatives, such as Corporate Social Marketing, Cause-Related Marketing, Cause Promotion, Corporate Philanthropy, Socially Responsible Business Practices, and Community Volunteering (Table 1).

Figure 1: Main CSR initiatives

Corporate Social Marketing	Cause Related Marketing	Cause Promotion	Corporate Philanthropy	Socially Responsible Business Practices	Community Volunteering
Promoting individual behavior change to improve public health or a social cause	Using sales business revenue to promote a specific cause	Promoting causes or providing paid sponsorships for causes	Providing direct donations to a charity or cause	Engaging in business practices that are associated with a societal good or social cause	Encouraging employees to volunteer in support of social causes

Source: Kotler and Lee (2005)

This paper will focus on a CSR initiative developed for Pakistani context. In this century, most of the successful businesses in this country are working on CSR. The reason is that government imposed CSR as an obligation.

In this paper, we have specifically selected the Coca-Cola Company Pakistan and Edhi Foundation Campaign, which was run in Pakistan in 2017, especially in the holy month of Ramazan. The main message of this campaign was “*Appealing to public consciousness will simply be that Edhi Sahab’s legacy and mission must carry on*” (Coca-Cola Journey, 2017).

2. Case development

CSR was a phenomenon that was born in the West and continues in Asian countries. In Pakistan, many of the successful organizations are focusing on CSR. Since 2017, Coca-Cola Company Pakistan has started the CSR campaign with the Edhi Foundation in Pakistan, which is titled “Bottle of Change”. This campaign is triumphant in Pakistan every year.

2.1. Coca-Cola Company in Pakistan

Coca-Cola Company is a renowned brand all around the world. It was introduced in Pakistan in 1953 and the first bottle plant was launched in the city of Karachi. In 1965, Coca-Cola Company also introduced Fanta; Sprite was introduced in 1972; and, after thirty years, Fanta Lemon and Diet Coke were introduced in 2001 (Coca Cola Journey, 2019). Nowadays, Coca-Cola beverages are manufactured and sold in Pakistan via the company’s own bottling plants which run under Coca-Cola Beverages Pakistan Ltd. The Coca-Cola Beverages Pakistan Ltd. plants are available in Karachi, Multan, Gujranwala, Hyderabad, Faisalabad, Lahore, Sialkot, and Rahim Yar Khan. In Pakistan, Coca-Cola’s local office focuses on marketing the company’s brands (UK Essay, 2018).

Currently, the Coca-Cola Company is promoting the sustainability strategy (Figure 2) with the name of “Live Positively”, which focuses on consumer well-being, customer value, human rights, human capital, environmental footprint, and community development. It is the cornerstone of the company Global 2020 vision. Coca-Cola Company proudly donates money to more than 200 countries and regions from all over the world (Coca-Cola Journey, 2019).

Figure 2: Coca Cola Sustainability Strategy

Source: CCI sustainability Report (2017)

2.2. Edhi Foundation

Abdul Sattar Edhi was a Pakistani and Muslim philanthropist, humanitarian and ascetic, who was the founder of “Edhi Foundation” (Figure 3). Edhi Foundation provides the world's largest volunteer ambulance network, homeless shelters, animal shelter, rehab centers and orphanages all around Pakistan (Edhi, 2019).

Figure 3: Edhi Foundation

Source: Edhi Foundation (2019)

Abdul Sattar Edhi was born in the small village of Bantva, Gujrat (India) in 1928. When Abdul Sattar was at the age of 11, his mother became partially paralyzed and with the passage of time, she got mentally sick (Edhi Foundation, 2019). He “devoted himself to looking after mother’s needs, bathing, cleaning, feeding, and clothing” (Edhi Foundation, 2019). When Abdul Sattar Edhi was at the age of 19, his mother passed away. His personal experience was made to think about that thousand and millions of people suffering like his mother, nobody to look of them (Edhi Foundation, 2019). So, Abdul Sattar Edhi became faithfully involved in the charity work and, after a while, Edhi established a welfare trust with the name of “Edhi Trust”.

The Vision of “Edhi Trust” is: “You have to care for all being created by God... My mission is to help to any person in need” (Edhi Foundation, 2019).

Nowadays, the Edhi Foundation is expanding all around Pakistan based on the social network. Edhi Foundation provides the different services, such as ambulance, hospital, children services, Edhi home, Orphanage Centres, Education Services, Graveyard, Marriage Bureau Services, Charitable Shop, Animal Hostel, Missing Personal Services, and Online Qurbani Service (Edhi Foundation, 2019) - Figure 4.

Figure 4: Edhi Foundation Services

Source: Edhi Foundation (2019)

Edhi Foundation is not only found for '*ashraf-ul-makhlookat*' (*Human Beings*), it also provides the services to the missing or innocent animals who had trampled on roads or on encountering a dead animal on a road, etc (Edhi Foundation, 2019). Abdul Sattar Edhi had also felt about the animals, most of the people never thinking about the animals. He personally carried almost a hundred of the dead animals and disposed of the animal's bodies.

Edhi's humanitarian work is not only for Pakistan. Edhi Foundation who provides the welfare services extend all over the world, such as the United Kingdom, the United States, Nepal, India, Canada, Sudan, Burma, Ethiopia, Uganda, UAE, Japan, Russia, Hungary, Bangladesh, Afghanistan, and Sri Lanka. Edhi services are available for all these countries (Natasha, 2010).

Edhi emphasizes "*Huqooq-ul-ibaad*" (the rights of fellow humans) being a means of completing "*Huquq Allah*" (the rights of God). According to Abdul Sattar Edhi, people focus on the ritualistic side of Islam: "*We verbally and ritualistically adopt Huquq Allah but ignore that Huquq-ul-Ibad is the fundamental principle that implements it*" (Natasha, 2010).

Edhi was passed away on July 8, 2016, at the age of 88, due to kidney failure. After the death of Abdul Sattar Edhi, the foundation declined up to 20 to 30 percent (Rajput, 2017).

2.3. Edhi Foundation and Coca-Cola Company Pakistan Join Hands for "Bottle of Change"

Son of late Abdul Sattar Edhi, Faisal Edhi (Head of the Foundation) collaborated with Coca-Cola Company Pakistan and launched the campaign with the name of "Bottle of Change" on 17th May 2017 (Figure 5).

"A key feature of the Coca-Cola campaign will double all donations received during the campaign up to a limit of Rs 25 million, apart from spending a very large sum on a multi-dimensional publicity campaign for this great humanitarian institution. Coca-Cola is going to double (2X) all the donations it gets from the people and donate it all to the Edhi Foundation by converting its bottle into money banks as the Bottle of Change" (Coca-Cola Journey, 2019). This campaign was multi-dimensional publicity all-round Pakistan in 2017.

The vital message of the campaign was "*to appeal public consciousness will simply be that Edhi Sahab's legacy and the mission must carry on*" (Coca-Cola Journey, 2019). While this, all around the Pakistan people have always committed with Edhi Foundation during the year, especially Holy Month of Ramazan. Because of the Holy Month of Ramazan, the people are more involved in donation and zakat (this is one of the Five Pillars of Islam, and the amount made under Islamic law on the specific property).

Figure 5: Press Conference in Karachi (Pakistan)

Source: Daily Time (2017)

3.3.1. First Campaign in 2017

2017 was the First Ramazan without the enlightened leadership of Abdul Sattar Edhi. This campaign had started in Ramazan 2017 with the name of “Bottle of Change”. This campaign was launched through social media with Coca Cola’s slogan “Eidi for Edhi”, while Edhi Foundation stated it as “Eidi for Edhi”, with the poem of “Lab Pe Aati Hai Dua”. This poem was written by Allama Iqbal in 1902. This poem’s meaning is “To my lips comes a prayer”. It is recited in every school in Pakistan (Propakistan, 2018). This song perfectly fit for Coca-Cola’s Ramazan Campaign “Eidi for Edhi”. This campaign video was flourishing in the Month of Ramazan. The “Bottle of Change” meaning is, Pakistan’s people collect the charities in the “Coca Cola Bottles” which shares to Edhi Centers (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Advertisement on Social Media

Source: Coca-Cola Journey (2018)

In this year, another video was launched with the Pakistani celebrities Maya Ali, Mikhaal Zulfiqar, Ali Sethi, Nadeem Baig, and Mahira Khan, with the slogan “Aao Jama Karain Insaniyat Keiye” (Let’s contribute to humanity) with the same cause (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Advertisement on Social Media

Source: Coca-Cola Journey (2018)

2.3.2. Second Campaign in 2018

2018 “Bottle of Change” campaign was very successful and people again moved towards the Edhi Foundation in the Holy Month of Ramazan. In this regard, this campaign was also launched in the Holy Month of Ramazan with the same core message, appealing with the same slogan “Eidi for Edhi”, and with

the same advertisement (1 min and 23 seconds) that in 2017. Pakistan's people were also given an encouraging and optimistic response.

2.3.3. Third Campaign in 2019

“Bottle of Change” campaign was also launched in 2019, in the Holy Month of Ramazan, with the same core message, appealing with the same slogan “Eidi for Edhi”, and with the same advertisement (1 min and 23 seconds). Pakistan's people have also given the same positive response.

2.3.4. 2018 Best Campaign in Asia

Coca-Cola Company Pakistan and Edhi Foundation Campaign advertisement was very successful all over the world because of the country's iconic social welfare organization, the Edhi Foundation. Coca-Cola Company Pakistan won the prestigious award “*Dragons of Asia Awards*” which ceremony held in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia 2018 (Figure 8).

Figure 8: 2018 Best Campaign In Asia

Source: Dragons of Asia (2018)

In 2018, “donations amount increased by almost 60% as per Ramzan projections. Coca-Cola donated 20 million Rupees. Moreover, all previous Ramazan season sales figures achieved by the brand were topped and a new milestone figure was achieved” (Global Village Space, 2018).

As a result, Coca-Cola Company Pakistan, who had taken the responsibility to carry out the Edhi mission, has created a stronger and healthier image and relationship with the consumers. Coca-Cola Company Pakistan also explained the Edhi Foundation mission all around the world through advertisement.

3. Questions for discussion

Question 1. *What do you think: Are religious people more involved in the “Coca-Cola & Edhi campaign” in the Holy month of Ramazan, in comparison to non-religious people?*

One of the five pillars of Islam is Zakat (every Muslim must pay 2.5% of the earned amount). In the Holy month of Ramazan, religious people think how to increase the SAWAB (reward) 700 times more. Therefore, religious people till more towards Zakat (charity) campaigns during the Holy month of Ramadan as compared to their non-religious fellows.

Consequently, three years developing the Coca-Cola company campaign of Edhi get more benefits in this month and generate more money to serve for orphans and homeless.

Question 2. *What do you think about the impact of the “Bottle of Change” campaign on public behavior?*

After Abdul Sattar Edhi's death, the people's behavior was changed towards Edhi for donation. The “Bottle of Change” campaign modified people's behavior again. The young generations (who drink more soft drinks) participated more “in a good cause” by buying Coca-Cola. Thus, the increase in Coca-Cola's sales was appreciated in Pakistan.

Question 3. Why Coca-Cola Company Pakistan has targeted this campaign in the Holy month of Ramazan?

The top management of Coca-Cola Company in Pakistan was well-aware of the increased charitable behavior of Muslims during the Holy month of Ramadan. Thus, they launched this campaign in the Holy month of Ramadan for achieving their sales targets as well as contributing towards this charitable cause.

Question 4. Do you think if another way to live the Edhi personality would be possible in the future?

Edhi was a well-known personality for this cause of helping others, and by using all the available resources instead of demanding more resources before helping others. If the Edhi campaign is running every year with the different organizations in the future, Edhi's personality will be alive.

Question 5. What do you think about people that bought Coca-Cola in the Holy Month of Ramazan? Was it for "Bottle of Change" campaign, or because they like to purchase the product in the Holy Month of Ramazan?

Coca-Cola Company is a renowned brand in the world, and its sales are very high. In every festival, Muslim people consume this product. Thus, Coca-Cola is also consumed in the Holy Month of Ramazan.

That is why this campaign is very successful, because of the link between Coca-Cola and Edhi Foundation.

4. Conclusions

The Coca-Cola Company Pakistan has a great chance to promote the company's "Sustainability Strategy". The Coca-Cola Company Pakistan already works with different CSR projects, but this project is very worthwhile because of Edhi's personality. Abdul Sattar Edhi is one of the biggest renowned names in all over the world. Most of the international countries give donations to Edhi Foundation.

The "Bottle of Change" campaign was specially launched in the Holy Month of Ramazan in Pakistan. The reason was that people in Pakistan are mostly attached to religion and they are giving the charity or donation to a different organizations or needed people.

After the Abdul Sattar Edhi's death, the people's behavior was changed towards Edhi for donation. The "Bottle of Change" campaign modified people's behavior and the people of Pakistan again move towards donations for Edhi Foundation. Thus, Coca-Cola Company Pakistan's mission "to appeal public consciousness will simply be that Edhi Sahab's legacy and mission must carry on", with this campaign, has been successful for the last three years.

Coca-Cola Company Pakistan will also carry out Edhi mission in different Islamic Festivals of Pakistan, such as *Eid-al-Adha*.

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